

EMBRACING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN EDUCATION SYSTEM AS A TREND FOR NATIONAL AND GLOBAL POLICY DEVELOPMENT

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In our interconnected global society, the ability to communicate effectively in foreign languages has become increasingly essential. Beyond simply being a means of communication, foreign languages play a crucial role in fostering cultural understanding, driving economic growth, and promoting international cooperation. From fostering diplomatic relations to enhancing economic competitiveness, proficiency in foreign languages is a vital component of a nation's global strategy. This article explores how embracing foreign languages as a trend can drive the development of robust national and global policies.

Key words: *Foreign Languages; Global Policies; Nationality; Economic Cooperation.*

1. Introduction

In our interconnected global society, the ability to communicate effectively in foreign languages has become increasingly essential. Beyond simply being a means of communication, foreign languages play a crucial role in fostering cultural understanding, driving economic growth, and promoting international cooperation [15]. According to Liddicoat [12], from fostering diplomatic relations to enhancing economic competitiveness, proficiency in foreign languages is a vital component of a nation's global strategy. Abadi [1], in his article adds that cultural understanding and empathy takes place in the integration of language. According to him, learning a foreign language goes beyond grammar and vocabulary; it opens doors to new cultures, traditions, and perspectives. When individuals engage with a foreign language, they gain insights into different ways of thinking and broaden their worldview. This cultural understanding fosters empathy, tolerance, and respect for diversity, which are fundamental values in the all-globalized society.

Peercy et al [18] argues that languages are also took responsible of global communication. It means that in an era where businesses operate on a global scale and international travel is commonplace, proficiency in foreign languages is a powerful asset. Being able to communicate with clients, partners, and colleagues in their native language builds trust, strengthens relationships, and facilitates smoother transactions. In diplomatic circles, language fluency is a prerequisite for effective negotiations and collaboration on global issues. Gay & Mills [9] adds that proficiency in foreign lan-

guages significantly enhances career opportunities across various sectors. Multinational corporations seek employees who can interact seamlessly with international clients and navigate cross-cultural environments. Moreover, in fields such as tourism, hospitality, journalism, and academia, language skills are often a requirement for career advancement and professional success.

2. Main materials

The importance of foreign languages extends far beyond linguistic proficiency. It encompasses cultural enrichment, professional opportunities, cognitive development, and global citizenship. As we navigate an increasingly interconnected world, investing in language education and promoting multilingualism is not just beneficial but imperative. Embracing linguistic diversity empowers individuals, bridges cultural divides, and paves the way for a more inclusive and prosperous global community [17; 11].

The national benefits of foreign language skills. Foreign language skills are not just a personal asset but also hold immense value at the national level. Countries that prioritize and invest in language education reap numerous benefits that contribute to their cultural, economic, and diplomatic prosperity. In Mitchell's [14] research about the connection between foreign languages skills to global communication abilities, they found that being proficient in foreign languages is a hallmark of global citizenship. It enables individuals to participate actively in global conversations, engage with diverse communities, and contribute meaningfully to cross-border initiatives. In an interconnected world facing complex challenges such as climate change, pandemics, and geopolitical tensions, linguistic competence fosters collaboration and solidarity among nations and peoples. Nizamuddin & Lailatur in their article "learning multiple foreign languages in community of practice" [17] describe the ways for improving the diplomatic relations between countries. they explain that proficiency in foreign languages strengthens a nation's diplomatic capabilities. Diplomats and foreign service officers who can communicate fluently in multiple languages build rapport, facilitate negotiations, and bridge cultural gaps effectively. This linguistic diplomacy fosters trust and cooperation between nations, leading to smoother diplomatic engagements and conflict resolution efforts.

Except that, Solmaz [19] describe the importance of economic Competitiveness. The foreign language skills play a pivotal role in driving economic competitiveness. Businesses that can engage with international markets in local languages gain a competitive edge. They can negotiate contracts, navigate regulatory environments, and tailor marketing strategies to specific cultural nuances. This linguistic agility expands export opportunities, attracts foreign investments, and boosts overall economic growth. Abadi [1] argue that a workforce with diverse language skills enhances a country's global talent pool. Multinational companies seek employees who can communicate with clients, partners, and colleagues from different linguistic backgrounds. By cultivating language skills domestically, nations can attract skilled workers, encourage innovation through cross-cultural collaboration, and strengthen their position in emerging industries and markets.

The author of the article also adds that Language proficiency facilitates meaningful cultural exchange and enhances a nation's soft power. Through literature, arts, music, and media in foreign languages, countries can showcase their cultural heritage and values to the world. This cultural diplomacy fosters mutual understanding, promotes tourism, and attracts international students, researchers, and cultural enthusiasts, thus enriching the national fabric.

The necessity of learning a foreign language. In a globalized society characterized by interconnectedness and cultural diversity. Beyond the practical benefits, such as enhanced career opportunities and improved cognitive abilities, learning a foreign language fosters cross-cultural understanding, promotes empathy, and opens doors to new experiences. De Garot & Barry [5] point in a main **mandatory characteristic** for learning a foreign language in educational systems:

a. **Global Communication.** Learning a foreign language facilitates effective global communication. In an era where businesses operate on an international scale and individuals travel across borders frequently, being able to speak another language breaks down barriers and enables meaningful interactions. Whether in business negotiations, academic collaborations, or personal relationships, linguistic proficiency enhances communication and strengthens connections with people from diverse backgrounds [1; 19].

b. **Cultural Understanding and Empathy.** One of the most significant benefits of learning a foreign language is the opportunity to gain insights into different cultures. Language and culture are intricately linked, and by learning a language, individuals also immerse themselves in the customs, traditions, and values of the speakers of that language. This cultural understanding fosters empathy, tolerance, and respect for diversity, which are essential qualities in a globalized world striving for harmony and mutual respect [7; 10; 8].

c. **Career Advancement.** Proficiency in a foreign language significantly enhances career prospects and advancement opportunities. Many industries value employees who can communicate in multiple languages, as it enables businesses to expand into new markets, cater to diverse customer bases, and forge international partnerships. Additionally, language skills are often a requirement for positions in diplomacy, international relations, tourism, and language-specific sectors such as translation and interpretation.

d. **Cognitive Benefits.** Learning a foreign language has been scientifically proven to have numerous cognitive benefits. It challenges the brain, improves memory retention, enhances problem-solving skills, and boosts overall cognitive function. Bilingual or multilingual individuals often exhibit greater mental agility, creativity, and adaptability, attributes that are highly valued in both professional and personal contexts [7].

e. **Personal Growth and Enrichment.** Beyond the practical advantages, learning a foreign language contributes to personal growth and enrichment. It broadens horizons, exposes individuals to new ideas and perspectives, and fosters a sense of curiosity and exploration. Language learners often develop a deeper appreciation for linguistic diversity, leading to a more inclusive and globally-minded outlook on life.

f. **National Security and Intelligence.** Foreign language skills are indispensable in the realm of national security and intelligence. Linguists proficient in critical lan-

guages aid in deciphering communications, analyzing geopolitical developments, and gathering intelligence vital for strategic decision-making. Investing in language education for defense personnel and intelligence agencies strengthens a nation's ability to address security threats proactively.

Strategic stages for embracing foreign languages in the education curriculum.

Integrating foreign languages into the education curriculum is a strategic decision that can yield significant benefits for students, society, and global engagement. However, to maximize the effectiveness of language learning, it's crucial to identify the right stages at which foreign languages should be introduced and integrated. *The first stage* is the early childhood education (Preschool to Elementary). According to Toohey [20], the first stage for embracing foreign languages in the education curriculum is during early childhood education, starting from preschool to elementary school. At this age, children are highly receptive to new languages and can acquire language skills more naturally. *The second stage* is primary education (Middle to Upper Elementary). In the primary education stage, which includes middle to upper elementary grades, foreign language instruction can be more structured and focused. Students can engage in formal language lessons that emphasize basic grammar, vocabulary expansion, and simple conversations [9]. *The third stage* is secondary education (Middle to High School). During secondary education, which spans from middle school to high school, foreign language learning progresses to a more advanced level. Students delve deeper into grammar rules, linguistic nuances, writing skills, and complex communication tasks [20; 7]. *The fourth stage* is higher Education and Lifelong Learning. In higher education institutions, foreign language education continues to play a vital role in preparing students for global citizenship and professional endeavors. Colleges and universities offer language courses tailored to students' academic disciplines, career goals, and international interest [9; 13]. *The last stage* is continuing education and community programs. Beyond formal education settings, lifelong learning opportunities for foreign languages are essential. Community programs, language centers, online platforms, and professional development courses cater to individuals of all ages who wish to enhance their language skills or learn new languages. These accessible avenues promote lifelong language learning, cultural engagement, and cross-cultural communication proficiency among learners of varying backgrounds and interests.

From the author experience (Lecturer of foreign languages; Kaye College; Israel), embracing foreign languages in the education curriculum involves a strategic progression that aligns with cognitive development, educational milestones, and lifelong learning principles. By introducing languages early, nurturing proficiency through structured learning stages, and providing continuous opportunities for language acquisition, societies can cultivate a multilingual and culturally competent populace. The right stages for embracing foreign languages in education not only empower individuals but also promote global understanding, collaboration, and interconnectedness in an increasingly diverse world.

Empowering Multilingualism - Encourage Foreign Language Learning Among Populations. According to Canagarajah [4], encouraging the learning of for-

eign languages among populations is not only beneficial for individuals but also crucial for fostering cultural understanding, global collaboration, and economic competitiveness. Bateman [3] Conduct research about the ideal process and conclude the following some conclusions.

One of the most effective ways to encourage foreign language learning is through early introduction in the education system. Schools should incorporate foreign language classes starting from elementary levels, exposing children to the sounds, vocabulary, and basic grammar of another language. Early exposure enhances language acquisition skills and fosters a positive attitude towards language learning from a young age.

He [3] also wrote about the culturally Immersive experiences. Organizing culturally immersive experiences can greatly motivate individuals to learn foreign languages. This includes study abroad programs, language immersion camps, and cultural exchange initiatives where participants are fully immersed in the target language and culture. Immersive experiences provide authentic language practice and deepen cultural understanding, making language learning more meaningful and enjoyable.

Dussel [6] in his article describe the technological Integration, which means that harnessing technology is essential in encouraging language learning among populations. Language learning apps, online courses, and interactive platforms offer convenient and accessible ways for individuals to engage with foreign languages. Garcia [8] talk about the community engagement and support. It means to creating a supportive language learning community is crucial for sustained motivation and progress. Language clubs, conversation groups, and language cafés provide opportunities for learners to practice speaking, receive feedback, and build confidence in using the language. Community support networks, including language mentors or tutors, can offer guidance and encouragement throughout the language learning journey.

If we look at on the issue of economic interest, we can point of integration into curricula and workforce Development. Integrating foreign language learning into academic curricula and workforce development programs is essential for long-term language proficiency. Schools, colleges, and vocational training institutions should offer language courses aligned with industry demands and global communication needs. Employers can support language training initiatives and provide language-learning opportunities as part of professional development plans [16].

3. Conclusions

According to the literature review, analyzing researches, and the author experience, encouraging foreign language learning among populations requires a comprehensive approach that combines educational initiatives, immersive experiences, technological tools, community support, recognition, and a focus on global citizenship. By implementing these effective strategies, societies can empower individuals to embrace multilingualism, bridge cultural divides, and thrive in an interconnected world rich in linguistic and cultural diversity.

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